

WAYS TO EXPAND NETWORK MARKETING AND E-COMMERCE IN WHOLESALE MEDICINES

Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna

Assistant professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7011955>

Abstract. *In this article, measures to strengthen the social protection of the population and provide medicines and medical products at low prices, support the pharmaceutical industry and fill the domestic market with domestic medicines and medical products, in particular, limited trade allowances in wholesale and retail trade, consider the system sale of socially significant medicines and medical products at established prices.*

Keywords: *pharmaceutical, industrial, wholesale and retail, sale, advertising, project, immunomodulator.*

ПУТИ РАСШИРЕНИЯ СЕТЕВОГО МАРКЕТИНГА И ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ В ОПТОВОЙ ТОРГОВЛЕ ЛЕКАРСТВАМИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены меры по усилению социальной защиты населения и обеспечению лекарственными средствами и изделиями медицинского назначения по низким ценам, поддержке фармацевтической отрасли и наполнению внутреннего рынка отечественными лекарственными средствами и изделиями медицинского назначения, в частности, ограниченные торговые надбавки в оптовой и розничной торговле, системная реализация социально значимых лекарственных средств и изделий медицинского назначения по установленным ценам.*

Ключевые слова: *фармацевтический, промышленный, опт и розница, продажа, реклама, проект, иммуномодулятор.*

INTRODUCTION

On the one hand, the activities of local drug manufacturers are aimed at the uninterrupted supply of the necessary drugs, and on the other hand, it saves a large amount of foreign currency. Providing the population of the country with high-quality medicines and medical supplies is one of the main directions in the development of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Measures have been taken to improve the price regulation system, support the pharmaceutical industry, fill the domestic market with domestic medicines and medical products in order to strengthen the social protection of the population and provide them with medicines and medical products at affordable prices. In particular, limited trade allowances were established for wholesale and retail trade, a system was introduced for the sale of socially significant medicines and medical products at fixed prices.

For effective advertising, it is recommended to use several channels at the same time:

Create an official website and develop its concept. Landing pages are suitable for promoting a specific product (biological supplements, drugs, vitamin complexes) - one-page sites. On the site, you can highlight the main advantages of the drug / manufacturer, show the composition, post reviews, leave a feedback form with customers.

Development of special projects. Closed medical blogs, channels on video hosting sites, and publications on third-party resources work well in this direction. For example, for the sale of

immunomodulators, you can create a collection of articles on strengthening immunity, where you can encourage people to buy the advertised product.

The development of social networks. Major pharmaceutical companies have long had Instagram pages, Facebook communities, and YouTube channels. When properly advertised, they convert well, increase brand awareness, and acquire loyal customers.

The pharmaceutical industry has been developing rapidly in recent years. In 2021, 220 local enterprises operated, including 101 pharmaceutical enterprises, 29 medical products, 82 medical products, 8 specializing in the production of medicines and medical products. There are 669 organizations in the pharmaceutical market that carry out wholesale and 13,957 retail sales of medicines and medical products.

The main idea of customer analysis is to get maximum information about customers from internal data. The source of such information in the pharmacy chain can be, in particular, checks. And if the network has a loyalty program, you may have even more opportunities for analysis and answers to many questions. Thanks to the collected data, the number of network shoppers, their characteristics (gender, age, frequency of purchases, average check, attitude to purchases, basket width, check length, etc.), consumption structure by region and point of sale, as well as targeted, up-to-date communication with opportunities clients.

RESULTS

Mutually beneficial cooperation between the network and the manufacturer for the exchange of information is possible. This is a big plus for the manufacturer, because a deep understanding of the characteristics of the end consumer allows more accurate planning of advertising and promotion activities, as well as communication with the end consumer on behalf of the pharmacy chain.

Of course, all clients are different. Therefore, in order to better understand the consumer and his needs, segmentation is used, which allows you to divide customers into different groups. Segmentation can be carried out according to various criteria - gender, age, geographical factor, lifestyle, etc. For segmentation, ABC-, RFM-analysis (English Recency Frequency Monetary - recipe, frequency, money) is used. Also in Western markets, segmentation by life cycle stages is popular.

The customer life cycle is a term that describes the stages in which a customer learns about a company's product, makes a purchase decision, pays, uses it, and becomes a loyal customer. In an ideal scenario, the value of the brand/company in the eyes of the buyer increases over time and he becomes a loyal customer, but often the value changes over time: the value either increases or decreases. Dependence on the change in the value of the client over time, as a rule, is depicted graphically. This is the customer lifecycle curve.

At different stages of the life cycle, communication strategies with customers can be different:

New clients: welcome program for new clients, newsletters.

Known active, stable customers: birthday greetings, loyalty program offers.

Inactive client (stopped being active for 3 months): reactivation programs, research and offers.

Lost client.

Of course, new clients will always appear, someone will leave, and someone will become a permanent core. How to understand how many customers are a stable core and how many

regular customers? The Leaky Bucket model helps to determine this. This model assumes that customers are divided into several groups depending on the stages of their life cycle. You can use names like "new", "stable", "churn", "random". Depending on the nature of behavior in different periods, the client falls into a certain segment. Thus, using the "leaky bucket" model allows you to understand the percentage of customer churn, how many new customers need to be attracted to cover the churn, etc.

It is desirable to understand the structure of the client's asset not only in terms of the stage of the life cycle or socio-demographic characteristics. After all, someone comes to the pharmacy for medicines, someone for vitamins, someone for care or medical cosmetics, someone for children's goods.

Therefore, it is inappropriate to offer the same offer to all customers. Instead, different offers and communication methods should be used for different customer groups. Clustering tools can be used to separate such groups.

Clustering is the process of dividing a given selection of objects into small sets (usually non-overlapping) called clusters, so that each cluster consists of similar objects, and the objects of different clusters are significantly different.

What is the difference between segmentation and clustering? Segments are predefined, but clusters are not. Clusters require a different interpretation than segments. In segmentation, the result is always predictable. On the other hand, clustering can be full of "surprises".

Clustering clearly defines the differences between clients, allows you to manage their heterogeneity. This tool will help you take a completely new look at the structure of customers and build relationships with consumers. The purpose of clustering is to extract new knowledge from your data. It's like finding treasure in the basement.

DISCUSSION

Understanding customers and their needs allows you to create targeted offers. The use of clustering for a loyalty program helps, in particular, to formulate a strategy for working with selected (priority) clusters, develop a communication plan with an emphasis on clusters, calculate the economics of working with clusters, simulate income and get additional income. income, develop cooperation

Digital marketing is a new stage in the development of the pharmaceutical industry in Uzbekistan. Pharmaceutical and medical organizations are beginning to take advantage of technological innovations that allow patients to receive more information about their condition and control their health, and doctors are given the opportunity to quickly communicate with patients throughout the entire treatment process.

Some pharmaceutical companies are trying to understand the true value of digital technology, while others are already incorporating it into their broader marketing strategy. However, not all companies can sell pharmaceutical products over the Internet because they produce prescription drugs that cannot be sold this way. However, they use digital methods to communicate with healthcare providers and patients. For example, Pfizer actively and promptly responds to customer inquiries through social media, using YouTube, Facebook and Twitter to communicate with customers. Johnson&Johnson was one of the first to launch its own YouTube channel.

More and more pharmaceutical organizations are using social media sites or e-commerce sites as digital marketing platforms to enable customers to learn about and order pharmaceutical products or buy products online.

Thanks to digitalization and modern communication technologies, behavioral changes in society enable consumers to receive services and purchase goods through the use of online services. Promotion of medicines, medical products, dietary supplements,

The use of pharmaceutical services, tools and methods of digital marketing on the Internet is a promising direction for the development of pharmaceutical organizations.

Electronic devices connected to the Internet have become an integral part of modern life, which contributes to an increase in the number of online orders in all industries.

CONCLUSIONS

Technological innovations in healthcare and pharmaceuticals allow patients to gain more information about their condition and take control of their health. New technologies allow doctors to constantly monitor the condition of patients, quickly communicate their messages and recommendations to them, and also give feedback on any side effects when using a particular drug therapy.

Mobile technologies, social networks and other forms of digital marketing are already enabling pharmacies and manufacturers of pharmaceutical and medical products to use a personalized approach to communication and information exchange with end consumers, and with the improvement of the regulatory framework, the professional community expects full personalization in the future pharmaceutical products, the possibility of care without distinction between offline and online interaction with the patient.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 17, 2017 "On additional measures to improve the system for providing the population with medicines and medical supplies" Solution #PQ-3137
2. Decree No. PF-5229 dated November 7, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the pharmacy chain management system".
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 20, 2018 No. PF-5460 "On measures to improve the efficiency of state registration of medicines and improve their provision to the population"
4. Decision No. PQ-4554 dated December 30, 2019 "On additional measures to deepen reforms in the pharmaceutical industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 21, 2022 No. PF-55 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2022-2026"
6. Philip Kotler. Kevin Lane Ketler. Sales management. Pearson Education, Inc. Prestige Hall, USA, 2012
7. Kotler F., Armstrong G., Wong W., Saunders D. Fundamentals of Marketing, 5th European ed. Textbook. - M.: LLC "ID Williams", 2013. - 752 p.
8. Soliev A., Vuzrukhanov S. Marketing, market science. Textbook. - T.: Economics-Finance, 2010. - 424 p.

9. Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.J., Kasimova M.S., Yusupov M.A. Marketing. Textbook. - T.: TDIU, 2011. - 202 p.
10. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kasimova M.S., Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.Zh. Strategic Marketing. Toolkit. 2010.-161 p.
11. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kasimova M.S., Safarov B.Zh., Musaeva Sh. Sales management. Toolkit. - T.: TDIU, 2007. 160 p.
12. Balashov A.I. Formation of a mechanism for sustainable development of the pharmaceutical industry. AVT. Dis. na sois., third degree den St. Petersburg - 2012.
13. Bobozhanov B. R. Statistical analysis and forecasting of the development of the pharmaceutical market in Uzbekistan. Scientific electronic journal "Economics and innovative technologies". No. 6, November-December 2020
14. B. Khamidov. The pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan in case of accession to the WTO. <https://review.uz/post/farmaceuticheskaya-otrasl-uzbekistana-pri-vstuplenii-v-vto>
15. Kovalnogova Yu.N. Organization of direct sales of pharmaceutical cosmetics, taking into account the factors of consumer behavior. AVT. Dis. on sois., 3. degree Ph.D. Ulyanovsk - 2018.
16. Wigglesworth, C., Zelser, J., The Health Supply Chain: Applying Best Practices to the Health Sector, in: Gattorna, J. (eds.), Jones, T., Dunks, A., Dillon, Y. . , Holdforth, L. (Associate Editor), Strategic Supply Chain Alignment: Best Practices in Supply Chain Management, Gower, Vermont, 1998, pp. 572-587.
17. eleven. <https://review.uz/oz/post/ozbekiston-eoiiga-azo-bolishining-farmaceutika-tarmogigatagir>.
18. Zueva D.S. Network marketing as an unconventional form of economic activity. Economic sociology. 6(4): 2005. 67-92. URL: <https://ecsoc.hse.ru/2005-6-4.html>
19. Kamushkina L. V. On the adaptive capabilities of the population in the system of network marketing. Sociological research. 2003.11: 142-145.
20. Safonova T. A. Sociological analysis of social practices of multi-level marketing. Abstract of dissertations on the study of the scientific steppe of the candidate of sociological sciences. Nizhny Novgorod. 2007.
21. Biggart SZ. Charismatic Capitalism: Direct Selling Organizations in America. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press. 1989
22. Bloom G. et al. 2011. Improving Health Markets for the Poor: The Case of Informal Providers. Health policy and planning; 26: i45-i52.
23. Yudanov A.Yu., Volskaya E.A., Ishmukhametov A.A., Denisova M.N. pharmaceutical marketing. Publishing house "Remedium". Moscow, 2008. 599 p.
24. O'G'Li F. S. E. et al. QISQA MUDDATLI HAYOT SUG 'URTASI MODELLARI //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. A3. – C. 146-149.
25. Fayzullayev S. E. O. G. L. Uchburchak elementlarining ba'zi bog'lanishlari haqida //Science and Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 4. – C. 27-32.